

The Effectiveness of Public Information and Documentation Officers (PPID) in Improving Public Services in Wonosobo Regency

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ABSTRACT: Public information disclosure is a crucial instrument for achieving transparent and accountable governance. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the Wonosobo Regency Information and Documentation Management Officer (PPID) in improving the quality of public services. The research method applied is a descriptive qualitative approach, with data collection carried out through interviews, observation, and documentation. The results indicate that the Wonosobo Regency PPID has carried out its strategic function in providing public information, increasing transparency, and innovating digital-based services. However, this effectiveness is not optimal due to limited human resources, inconsistent data updates at the assistant PPID, and coordination between regional government agencies (OPDs), which still needs to be strengthened. This study concludes that the effectiveness of the Wonosobo Regency PPID is quite effective and requires strengthening of its institutional capacity.

KEYWORDS: PPID; public information disclosure; organizational effectiveness; public services

I. INTRODUCTION

Public information disclosure has become a global agenda within public administration reform and the implementation of good governance principles. Information transparency is widely regarded as a key mechanism for enhancing governmental accountability, strengthening public participation, and improving the quality of public services. In Indonesia, the state's commitment to public information disclosure is formally affirmed through Law Number 14 of 2008 on Public Information Disclosure. As the technical implementers of information openness, public institutions are required to ensure the provision of high-quality information. Quality information is defined as information that is useful to its users and supported by three fundamental pillars: relevance, accuracy, and timeliness (Purnama, 2016). Consequently, information must be managed through appropriate systems to ensure that these quality standards are consistently achieved.

A system is defined as a set of interrelated components with clearly defined boundaries that work together to achieve common objectives by receiving inputs and producing outputs through an organised transformation process (Sudirman et al., 2020). An information system, whether computer-based or manual, consists of a collection of components designed to collect, manage, and store data, as well as to provide information outputs to users (Abdullah, 2015). Proper management of information systems enables organisations to generate accurate performance-related information, thereby supporting decision-making in both daily operational activities and long-term strategic planning. This perspective is consistent with Aswati et al. (2015), who argue that information systems contribute to organisational effectiveness by reducing costs, minimising errors, accelerating operational activities, and improving managerial planning and control.

At present, many government institutions have adopted information systems to monitor governmental performance at both central and local levels. This development is in line with Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2003 on the National Policy and Strategy for E-Government Development, which emphasises that the utilisation of information and communication technology in governance processes (e-government) promotes transparency and facilitates access to information for both government institutions and the general public. The effective implementation of e-government requires well-structured and reliable information systems to support government institutions in performing their public service functions.

Public Information and Documentation Officers (PPID) play a strategic role as the frontline actors in the implementation of public information disclosure within government institutions. The establishment of PPID is intended to ensure the availability of public information, accelerate responses to information requests, and enhance transparency and accountability in public administration. Accordingly, the effectiveness of PPID constitutes a critical factor in improving public service quality, particularly in the provision of information services to citizens. Nevertheless, empirical studies indicate that PPID implementation at the local government level continues to face several challenges. These challenges include limitations in human resources, suboptimal coordination among regional government agencies, inadequate updating of public information, and the underutilisation of

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information technology. Such conditions result in less effective public information services, which ultimately affect public satisfaction with government performance.

At the local government level, including in Wonosobo Regency, PPID has been formally established and operates through various service channels, both direct and digital. The local government has also introduced several innovations to improve the accessibility of public information. However, the extent to which PPID effectively performs its functions in enhancing public service quality still requires in-depth analysis based on empirical field conditions. Previous studies on PPID have generally focused on normative aspects, regulatory compliance, or technical evaluations of public information services. In contrast, studies that specifically analyse the effectiveness of PPID in relation to public service improvement, particularly at the regency level, remain relatively limited. This situation indicates a research gap that necessitates comprehensive investigation of PPID effectiveness from institutional, resource-based, service system, and public perception perspectives.

Based on these considerations, this study is important for analysing the effectiveness of Public Information and Documentation Officers (PPID) in improving public services. The study is expected to provide empirical evidence of PPID performance, identify factors that support and hinder its effectiveness, and formulate strategic recommendations to strengthen the role of PPID in delivering transparent and high-quality public services. Furthermore, this research contributes to addressing the existing research gap on PPID effectiveness at the local government level, particularly within the context of public services based on information disclosure.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Public Information Disclosure and the Role of PPID

Public information disclosure constitutes a fundamental principle in the administration of democratic governance and represents a core element of good governance. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2008 on Public Information Disclosure stipulates that every citizen has the right to obtain public information in a timely, accurate, and appropriate manner, while public bodies are obliged to provide and serve such information. Public Information and Documentation Officers (PPID) are formally established entities within public institutions responsible for managing and providing public information in accordance with statutory mandates. The implementation of PPID is intended to strengthen governmental transparency and accountability in public information services. Empirical studies on PPID implementation across various institutions indicate variations in execution and impact on public service delivery. Through the presence of PPID, the public is expected to access information more efficiently, which in turn contributes to the overall improvement of public service quality. This aligns with the principles of information openness that promote increased public trust and the consolidation of democratic processes.

B. Organisational Effectiveness and Public Services

Organisational effectiveness refers to the extent to which an organisation is able to achieve its predetermined objectives and fulfil stakeholder needs efficiently and appropriately. Theories of effectiveness have been developed in both public and private organisational contexts, emphasising goal attainment, internal functional integration, adaptability to environmental change, and responsiveness to societal demands. In the context of public services, effectiveness specifically denotes an institution's capacity to deliver services in accordance with standards of timeliness, accuracy, accessibility, and user satisfaction. Within public administration scholarship, improvements in the effectiveness of state institutions are assessed not only through administrative performance indicators but also through public perceptions of service quality. Effective public service delivery reflects service processes that are responsive to community needs and consistent with transparency principles.

C. Effectiveness of PPID in Public Information Services

A number of empirical studies have examined the effectiveness of PPID within the context of public information services at both regional and institutional levels. Pramesti and Mardhatillah (2023) analysed the effectiveness of the PPID application implemented by the Department of Communication and Informatics of West Tanjung Jabung Regency. Their findings indicate that the effectiveness of the PPID application remained suboptimal due to several technical and operational constraints, including delays in processing information requests, insufficient socialisation, and limitations in human resources and supporting infrastructure. These findings suggest that PPID effectiveness does not depend solely on the existence of digital applications, but also on the organisational capacity to manage information service processes in an integrated manner.

Similarly, Amelia et al. (2025) found that E-PPID services at the Audit Board of Indonesia (BPK) Representative Office of Central Kalimantan Province met certain effectiveness indicators, particularly in terms of service goal achievement and procedural integration. However, challenges related to limited socialisation continued to hinder optimal utilisation of the service. This study highlights the need to enhance digital literacy and community engagement in order to achieve higher levels of effectiveness in E-PPID implementation.

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D. The Role of PPID and Information Transparency

Research examining the role of PPID across various regions provides insights into its contribution to the realisation of public information transparency. For instance, Aprilya and Fadhlain (2022) demonstrated that PPID in Simeulue Regency functioned as a coordinator of information services among regional government agencies. However, its performance was constrained by limited dissemination of information and the suboptimal functioning of assistant PPIDs. This finding indicates that the role of PPID in public services encompasses a critical coordinative dimension necessary to support effective information disclosure. Likewise, a study by Waskito and Kholifah (2024) in Jember Regency revealed that public information transparency resulting from PPID programme implementation constitutes an essential component of public service delivery. The study emphasised that information disclosure requires not only data provision but also effective management of communication processes between public institutions and the community.

E. Challenges to PPID Effectiveness in Public Services

Studies focusing on optimising PPID performance in improving public services also reveal several persistent challenges. Nurrahman et al. (2022) found that although the PPID application had been implemented in Kebumen Regency, aspects such as service socialisation, public awareness of information disclosure, and the active role of assistant PPIDs remained underdeveloped. Consequently, the effectiveness of public information services required further improvement. These findings reinforce the argument that the success of PPID in enhancing public services is strongly influenced by institutional factors, internal communication, and public understanding. Furthermore, research on public information service management within the government of Cilegon City demonstrates that effective information services are built upon sound management practices, including planning, coordination, and the implementation of information disclosure procedures in accordance with prevailing regulations. This underscores that PPID effectiveness is inseparable from overall organisational management capacity.

Based on the above literature review, PPID effectiveness emerges from the interaction between institutional mechanisms such as human resources, service procedures, and information systems public perception and participation, and the support of information technology. Effective PPID implementation enhances accessibility, transparency, and public satisfaction with information services, which in turn contributes to overall public service quality. Organisational effectiveness refers to the degree of success an organisation achieves in fulfilling its objectives. Steers (1985) emphasises that effectiveness is influenced by organisational structure, resource availability, and internal coordination. In the public service context, effectiveness is closely associated with the quality of services as perceived by the community. Public information disclosure represents one of the main pillars of good governance. Douglas (2016) demonstrates that government transparency significantly contributes to public value creation and increased public trust. Comparative studies by Khosrowjerdi (2022) also reveal a positive relationship between good governance practices and levels of information transparency across countries. Moreover, the effective utilisation of public information systems has been shown to enhance governmental transparency and accountability (Panggabean et al., 2025). Accordingly, PPID effectiveness is determined not only by regulatory compliance but also by institutional capacity and the support of information technology.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a descriptive qualitative research approach. The research was conducted at the Department of Communication and Informatics of Wonosobo Regency, which functions as the Main Public Information and Documentation Officer (PPID), as well as several Regional Government Agencies (Organisasi Perangkat Daerah/OPD) acting as Assistant PPID units. Informant selection was carried out using purposive sampling, whereby individuals with in-depth knowledge of the research issues were deliberately selected. In addition, snowball sampling was applied to allow the number of informants to expand in accordance with the data requirements identified during the research process.

Data were collected through observation, interviews, and documentation related to the research focus. The research subjects comprised the Main PPID, Assistant PPIDs, and applicants for public information services. Data collection techniques included in-depth interviews, direct observation of public information services, and document analysis. To ensure data validity, triangulation techniques were employed. Specifically, both source triangulation and method triangulation were applied, as the use of multiple data sources and collection techniques enhances the credibility and trustworthiness of qualitative findings.

Data analysis followed the interactive model proposed by Miles and Huberman, which consists of three main stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing and verification. Data credibility was further ensured through the consistent application of source triangulation and methodological triangulation throughout the research process.

IV. RESUOLT AND DISCUSSION

The Public Information and Documentation Officer (PPID) of Wonosobo Regency was established as the technical implementer of public information disclosure in accordance with Law Number 14 of 2008 on Public Information Disclosure. The Main PPID

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operates under the coordination of the Department of Communication and Informatics of Wonosobo Regency and is supported by Assistant PPIDs within each Regional Government Agency (Organisasi Perangkat Daerah/OPD). Observational findings indicate that the PPID has established an organisational structure, standard operating procedures (SOPs), and public information service channels, both through direct services and digital platforms via the official PPID website. Public information services are provided through the receipt of information requests, verification processes, and the delivery of information to applicants in compliance with prevailing regulations.

Document analysis reveals that the PPID of Wonosobo Regency has made available public information classified as periodic information, immediate information, and information available at all times. The information provided includes institutional profiles, local government programmes and activities, financial reports, and regional legal products. However, the availability and completeness of information are not evenly distributed across all Assistant PPIDs. Several OPDs have not updated their information on a regular basis, resulting in some data that do not fully reflect current conditions.

Based on records of public information requests, most requests were completed within three to five working days. This processing time remains within the service timeframe stipulated by the Public Information Disclosure Law. Information services are delivered in accordance with established SOPs. Nevertheless, some information requests experienced delays due to the need for further coordination with Assistant PPIDs in the relevant OPDs.

The findings indicate that the PPID of Wonosobo Regency has implemented transparency principles by publishing lists of public information, annual PPID reports, and recapitulations of public information requests. These materials are accessible through online media. However, reporting and information submission from Assistant PPIDs to the Main PPID have not been carried out consistently across all OPDs, which has affected the overall integration of public information data.

Observations show that the PPID of Wonosobo Regency has utilised information technology through the development of a PPID website and an online public information request system. This service facilitates public access to information and simplifies the submission of information requests. Despite these developments, the utilisation of information technology has not yet been fully optimised. Some service features remain underutilised, and a segment of the public continues to prefer face-to-face services.

Interviews with public information applicants indicate that most respondents expressed positive perceptions of PPID services, particularly regarding staff friendliness and the clarity of service procedures. However, several respondents raised concerns related to the completeness of available information and the length of service processing time in certain cases.

The availability and completeness of public information constitute the primary indicators of PPID effectiveness. The findings indicate that the PPID of Wonosobo Regency has provided most of the public information mandated by prevailing regulations. This demonstrates that the PPID has made substantial efforts to fulfil its institutional mandate as a public information service provider. However, uneven information updating among Assistant PPIDs suggests that PPID effectiveness remains influenced by institutional coordination factors. This finding is consistent with organisational effectiveness theory, which emphasises the importance of integration and alignment among organisational units in achieving institutional objectives.

The speed of public information services reflects the level of responsiveness of public organisations to community needs. The results show that the PPID of Wonosobo Regency is generally able to process information requests within the legally prescribed timeframe, indicating a satisfactory level of responsiveness. Nevertheless, delays in certain cases reveal that PPID responsiveness is still affected by internal coordination mechanisms and data readiness at the relevant OPDs. This finding reinforces the view that public service effectiveness is determined not only by the existence of standard operating procedures, but also by the capacity and commitment of human resources.

The implementation of transparency and accountability through the publication of public information lists and service reports reflects the PPID's efforts to build public trust. Transparency is a core principle of good governance that promotes openness and governmental accountability. However, inconsistencies in reporting practices among Assistant PPIDs indicate that transparency has not yet been fully institutionalised across all organisational units. This condition highlights the need to strengthen supervision, guidance, and institutional capacity-building for Assistant PPIDs.

The use of information technology in PPID services represents an important innovation for enhancing accessibility and efficiency in public service delivery. The findings demonstrate that online PPID services have facilitated public access to information. However, the effectiveness of digital innovation remains constrained by varying levels of public digital literacy and suboptimal utilisation of service features. Therefore, the development of information technology must be accompanied by continuous capacity-building for personnel and systematic public outreach to maximise service utilisation.

Public satisfaction reflects the ultimate outcome of effective public information services. The findings indicate that the majority of service users expressed satisfaction with PPID services, although several aspects still require improvement. This result aligns with public service theories that position user satisfaction as a key indicator of organisational performance in the public sector. Consequently, efforts to enhance the quality of PPID services should be pursued on a continuous basis.

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Overall, the effectiveness of the PPID of Wonosobo Regency in improving public service delivery can be categorised as moderately effective. The PPID has generally fulfilled its public information service functions in accordance with regulatory requirements, yet continues to face challenges related to institutional coordination, technology utilisation, and consistency in information updating. The findings show that most mandatory public information has been made available through online platforms, with average response times remaining within statutory limits. Digital service innovations have contributed positively to improved information accessibility.

Nevertheless, PPID effectiveness has not yet reached an optimal level due to limitations in human resources, disparities in information management quality among Assistant PPIDs, and the need for stronger inter-agency coordination. These findings are consistent with organisational effectiveness theory, which underscores the critical role of resource availability and internal coordination in achieving organisational goals.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research findings and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of the Public Information and Documentation Officer (PPID) in Wonosobo Regency has been **moderately effective** in improving public service delivery. The PPID has generally fulfilled its core mandate in providing and delivering public information in accordance with Law No. 14 of 2008 on Public Information Disclosure. From the perspective of information availability and completeness, most mandatory public information—periodic, immediate, and on-demand—has been provided. However, inconsistencies in information updating among Assistant PPIDs indicate that the accuracy and timeliness of information remain uneven.

In terms of service timeliness and responsiveness, the majority of public information requests were processed within the legally prescribed timeframe, reflecting an adequate level of organisational responsiveness. Transparency and accountability have also been demonstrated through the publication of public information lists and annual PPID reports. Nevertheless, limited compliance and coordination among Assistant PPIDs have constrained the full integration of public information management. In addition, although the utilisation of information technology through online services has improved accessibility, its effectiveness is still influenced by uneven digital literacy and the suboptimal use of available service features.

Overall, the effectiveness of PPID has contributed positively to the quality of public information services and public satisfaction. However, further improvements are required, particularly in strengthening human resource capacity, enhancing inter-agency coordination, and developing an integrated information system. These measures are essential to ensure that PPID effectiveness can be achieved more optimally and sustained over the long term.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to express sincere gratitude to the Department of Communication and Informatics of Wonosobo Regency, as the Main Public Information and Documentation Officer (PPID), along with all Assistant PPIDs within the Regional Government Agencies, for their cooperation and support during the research process. Appreciation is also extended to all informants and public information service users who willingly shared their time, experiences, and insights, which were essential to the completion of this study.

The author also acknowledges the contributions of colleagues and parties who provided constructive feedback and assistance throughout the data collection and analysis stages. Any errors or limitations that remain in this article are entirely the responsibility of the author.

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